

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF BEETROOT AND AMLA BASED NUTRACEUTICAL TABLETS

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Article Received on 25 May 2026,

Article Revised on 15 June 2026,

Article Published on 01 July 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21027064>

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How To Cite This Article: Aditi Sharma^{1*}, Prof. (Dr.) Pankaj Kumar Sharma², Prof. (Dr.) Jaya Sharma³, Prof. Ms. Shashi Bhandari⁴ (2026). Formulation And Evaluation Of Beetroot And Amla Based Nutraceutical Tablets. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(7), 713–720.

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ABSTRACT

This study involved the formulation and evaluation of nutraceutical tablets containing beetroot and amla. Beetroot and amla are known for their nutritional and health-promoting properties because of natural phytoconstituents, vitamins, minerals, and bioactive compounds. The objective of the work was to develop a simple herbal nutraceutical tablet formulation and evaluate its basic pharmaceutical properties. Beetroot powder, amla powder, starch, ascorbic acid, and other additives are used in the formulation, and these tablets were made by the hand-rolling formula after proper blending and wet mass formation. The prepared tablets were evaluated for organoleptic characteristics, weight variation, hardness, and friability. The tablet shows an acceptable appearance, smooth surface, satisfactory hardness, uniform thickness, and acceptable friability values. The average weight of the tablet was 500.2mg, the hardness was 4.34 kg/cm², and the friability was 0.76%. The result is that the nutraceutical tablet manufacture is likely to have acceptable pharmaceutical characteristics and may serve as a potential herbal nutraceutical formulation.

KEYWORDS: Beetroot, Amla, Nutraceutical tablets, Herbal formulation, Tablet evaluation, Herbal nutraceuticals.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, people are more interested in maintaining health, and nutraceutical products are becoming popular because they provide nutritional and health benefits. Nutraceuticals are products derived from food sources and are increasingly used in preventive health care and nutritional supplementation.^[1,2] Herbal nutraceutical formulations are considered safer and more economical than synthetic formulations, and their demand is also increasing rapidly as awareness of natural health care systems and preventive medicine continues to grow.

Beetroot (*Beta vulgaris*) is a highly nutritious vegetable that is rich in vitamins, minerals, betalains, natural pigments, dietary fibers, and phenolic compounds. Beetroot contains essential nutrients such as iron, folic acid, potassium, magnesium, and vitamin C.^[3,4] Beetroot is also recognized for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cardioprotective properties due to the presence of betalains and polyphenolic compounds.^[14,15] It is also used for diet and as a nutritional supplement.

Amla (*Emblica officinalis*), also known as Indian gooseberry, is an important medicinal plant used in the Indian systems of medicine and is rich in vitamin C, polyphenols, tannins, amino acids, and minerals.^[5] Amla has been extensively studied for its antioxidant potential and its role in supporting immune function and overall health.^[16,17] It is used in herbal formulations because of its nutritional and therapeutic significance.

Tablet dosage forms are preferred in pharmaceutical formulations because they are more convenient, stable, portable, patient-compliant and accurate for dosing. Nutraceutical tablets are made from natural plant materials and are easy to incorporate herbal ingredients. The growing demand for herbal nutraceutical products has encouraged the development of innovative dosage forms such as tablets, capsules, and gummies for improved patient compliance.^[18]

The present study was undertaken to formulate and evaluate beetroot and amla-based nutraceutical tablets using simple pharmaceutical techniques. The prepared tablets were evaluated for various pharmaceutical parameters, including organoleptic properties, weight variation, hardness, thickness and friability.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To nutraceutical tablets containing beetroot and amla.
2. To make tablets by the hand rolling method.
3. To evaluate prepared tablets for pharmaceutical parameters.
4. To study the physical characteristics of the prepared tablets.

MATERIALS

The materials used in the present study are listed below

Table 1: Composition of Beetroot and Amla-Based Nutraceutical Tablets.

S. No.	Ingredient	Quantity (mg)	Quantity (g)
1	Beetroot powder	2750 mg	2.75 g
2	Amla powder	700 mg	0.7 g
3	Starch	1300 mg	1.3 g
4	Ascorbic acid	150 mg	0.15 g
5	Talc	100 mg	0.1 g

Beetroot and amla were procured from the local market of Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

DRYING OF RAW MATERIALS

The raw materials were first dried in the sun, although complete drying was not achieved by sun drying alone. Similar studies on the influence of drying methods on the properties of beetroot powder have been reported.^[6] Thus, both beetroot and amla materials were placed in a hot-air oven for 20 minutes to remove all moisture.

Before drying in the hot-air oven, the beetroot weighed 20.15 g, and the amla weighed 10.15 g. After drying in the hot-air oven, 5% reduction in weight was observed, indicating effective removal of moisture.

Figure 1: Dried Beetroot and Amla Raw Materials Used in Formulation.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Figure 2: Preparation Process of Beetroot and Amla Nutraceutical Tablets.

After purchasing from the market, beetroot and amla materials were initially dried in the sunlight, but complete drying was not achieved. Therefore, additional oven drying was carried out for 20 minutes to eliminate the remaining moisture. The dried materials were ground into fine powder and passed through a sieve. 44 to ensure a uniform particle size. Beetroot powder, amla powder, starch, ascorbic acid, and talc were correctly weighed according to the formulation composition. Starch was used as a preservative, so it was added to the beetroot and amla powder and mixed uniformly for 5 minutes. Ascorbic acid was included in the geometric dilution method to ensure uniform distribution within the formulation. Talc was added during the final blending stage and mixed uniformly for 5 minutes again. Distilled water was added dropwise to prepare a wet mass, which was mixed to obtain a uniform dough-like consistency. The prepared mass was divided into equal portions, and tablets were prepared by applying a little starch to the palm and then rolling it through the hands. The tablets were dried at room temperature for 24 hours, then after applying starch to the butter paper, the prepared tablets were stored in airtight containers under cool, dry conditions.

EVALUATION OF TABLETS

Organoleptic properties: The prepared tablets were evaluated for colour, odour, taste, shape, and surface.^[7,8]

Colour - Dark reddish brown to slightly black (A slight blackish colour was observed due to the over-drying of amla), Odour - Characteristic, Taste - Slightly sour, Shape - Round, Surface – Smooth.

Weight variation test: Ten tablets were selected and weighed individually.

Table 2: Weight Variation of Prepared Tablets.

Tablet no.	Weight (mg)
1	500
2	500
3	501
4	499
5	500
6	501
7	501
8	500
9	499
10	501

The average weight of the tablets was 500.2 mg.

Interpretation – The tablets showed uniformity in weight as per standard pharmaceutical guidelines with acceptable weight variation limits.^[8]

Hardness test: The hardness of tablets was determined using the hardness testing method.

Table 3: Hardness of Prepared Tablets.

Trial	Hardness (kg/cm ²)
1	4.2
2	4.5
3	4.3
4	4.1
5	4.6

Average hardness = 4.34 kg/cm²

Interpretation – The prepared tablets contain satisfactory mechanical strength and adequate resistance to handling. Similar hardness characteristics are considered important for tablet stability and handling properties.^[9]

Friability test: The friability test was performed to determine the mechanical resistance of tablets.

Table 4: Friability Test of Prepared Tablets.

Parameter	Value
Initial weight	6.50 g
Final weight	6.45 g
Friability	0.76%

Interpretation – The friability value was found to be less than 1%, indicating acceptable resistance.^[8,10]

Disintegration test: Disintegration time = 2min 15 sec

Interpretation – The prepared tablets showed satisfactory disintegration.

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED DURING FORMULATION

During formulation, difficulties arose because the beetroot and amla materials were not completely dried in the sun; they had to be dried in the hot air oven to obtain a suitable dry powder for tablet preparation. Amla became slightly darker after being placed in the hot air oven, possibly due to heat exposure.

Variability in tablet yield was also observed during the rolling with the palm. The formulation batch was 10 tablets, but a total of 12 tablets were observed, possibly due to manual division or weight mass distribution.

After making the tablet, it was kept in the refrigerator, so its disintegration time was 2 minutes and 15 seconds. Perhaps being kept in the fridge, its moisture content was lost, and the tablet became a little hard.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The present study was carried out to formulate and evaluate a beetroot and amla-based nutraceutical tablet. Organoleptic properties indicate that the colour is acceptable, the tablet has a characteristic odour, a smooth surface and a round shape. A slight blackish colour is also observed due to additional oven drying. The average weight of the tablet is 500.2mg, with good uniformity. Hardness value is also appropriate for the mechanical strength required for storage or handling. The friability value of 0.76% also indicates that the tablets show acceptable resistance to erosion and mechanical stress. The same pharmaceutical evaluation has also been studied for herbal and nutraceutical tablet formulations.^[11,12]

The overall evaluation results show that the prepared nutraceutical tablet has satisfactory pharmaceutical characteristics.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated beetroot and amla based nutraceutical tablets using simple pharmaceutical techniques. The prepared tablets showed satisfactory organoleptic and pharmaceutical properties including acceptable weight variation, hardness, thickness, and friability. The formulation demonstrated the feasibility of developing herbal nutraceutical tablets using natural ingredients. The prepared tablets may serve as a promising nutraceutical

formulation for future studies. Further optimization and advanced evaluation studies may improve the pharmaceutical performance and stability of the developed formulation.^[13]

FUTURE SCOPE

1. Antioxidant activity studies may be performed in future.
2. Dissolution studies can be carried out for detailed evaluation.
3. Stability studies may be conducted to determine shelf life.
4. Advanced analytical characterization may be performed.
5. In-vivo studies may be conducted to evaluate therapeutic benefits.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express sincere gratitude to Apex Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Apex University, Jaipur, for providing the necessary facilities and support to carry out this research work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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